

Tackling microplastic pollution with Nature-Based Solutions from urban runoff and wastewater

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ABSTRACT

1. Introduction.

The substantial population growth in cities has resulted in an increase in both wastewaters directed towards urban WWTPs and impermeable surfaces, leading to increased runoff during rainy episodes. This has led to the discharge of many pollutants, affecting and degrading surface waters.

Furthermore, millions of tons of plastic are produced annually, and this has also been increasing each year (Plastic Europe, 2021). As a consequence, a wide range of plastic debris are accumulating in the biosphere (terrestrial and marine), which can be fragmented into smaller pieces, known as microplastics (MPs). These tiny plastic particles, measuring less than 5 mm, can transport other pollutants, such as heavy metals (Sarkar et al., 2021) or persistent organic pollutants, among others. Their presence in organisms has been linked to reduced growth, reproductive issues, intestinal damage, and even death. Moreover, MPs contribute to the overall degradation of water quality, disrupt ecosystems, and have long-lasting environmental consequences, making them a significant environmental concern worldwide (Lu et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2019).

The primary objective of this project is to assess the retention of MPs from both wastewater and stormwater generated in urban environments through the use of various Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), such as Treatment Wetlands (TW) and Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS), with a particular focus on Vegetated Swales (VS). Two TW and two VS located in the province of Valencia (Spain) are evaluated within this work.

2. Methodology and results.

With respect to the TW, they have exhibited commendable efficiency in intercepting MPs. In this instance, two treatment plants were examined, one employing TW for both secondary and tertiary treatment, and another utilizing an aerated biological reactor with floating helophytes situated upon a buoyant structure as secondary treatment, along with TW for tertiary treatment (Fig. 1). Water samples were collected at the inlet and outlet of both WWTPs, as well as at intermediate points (inlet and outlet of TWs), in order to accurately quantify the efficiencies. Additionally, samples were taken from the sludge of the secondary treatments of both plants, and root samples were also collected to study their potential retention effect.

Fig. 1. Scheme of both WWTPs studied, with the red points where samples were taken.

Two VS are currently under study. These systems are mature, having been in place for over ten years. One of them receives runoff from sports facilities and shared green areas, while the other collects water from both roadways and pedestrian zones. Figure 2 displays both zones and the adjacent areas that contribute runoff to them during rainfall events. In this case, the evaluation encompasses both the water at their inlet and outlet points, as well as soil samples taken at three zones (initial, intermediate, and final sections) within each of them. Given that these systems are open and more accessible to the public, an assessment of their content in macroplastics (MAPs) and mesoplastics (MEPs) (ranging from 5 to 25 mm) was also conducted.

Fig. 2. Both VS studied (yellow zones) with the contributing areas (blue zones) and the sample points numbered.

Regarding the methodology employed, the steps outlined in previous studies have been adhered to (Cabrera et al., 2023). Additionally, it is pertinent to continue with the same techniques that have been utilized in various studies.

The following are results from the studies conducted thus far. Firstly, the average retention efficiencies in water samples are presented for both WWTPs employing TW, as well as the concentrations obtained in sediment samples and within the vegetation roots inside of the TWs themselves (Fig. 3). Furthermore, the average results of MPs in water samples obtained in two sampled rainfall events in the VS are displayed, along with the results of MAPs and MEPs obtained in soil (Table 1).

Fig. 3. MPs concentration in the different points in both WWTPs (WWTP1 right and WWTP2 left). Concentrations measured in both WWTPs in sludge and roots samples.

Table 1. MAPs and MEPs concentrations in soil samples of both VS. Additionally, concentration of MPs and classification for water samples taken during two rainfall events in VS1.

Soil Sample	MAPs Total	MAP/m ²	MEPs/kg dw	Water Sample	Fibers	Particles	Films	MPs/L
VS1.1	27	4.5	8.5	Inlet	425 μm	17.5	5.5	0.5
VS1.2	27	4.5	200.8		75 μm	20	5.5	1
VS1.3	65	5.2	20.4		40 μm	12	4	0.5
VS2.1	20	6.7	11.8	Outlet	425 μm	6.5	0.5	0
VS2.2	116	38.7	22.2		75 μm	10	1	1
VS2.3	10	3.3	343.2		40 μm	6	0	0.5

In conclusion, the study suggests that both TWs and VS hold significant potential for retaining MPs. The initial findings underscore the importance of this issue, as the presence of MPs in both SUDS infrastructures built over a decade ago and in wastewater is notable.

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